

Prevalence and Antimicrobial Resistance Profiling of *Escherichia Coli* and *Staphylococcus Aureus* in Leafy Vegetables from Open Markets in Abakaliki, Nigeria: Implications for Food Safety and Public Health

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Abstract

Leafy vegetables are an essential component of a healthy diet; however, they can harbour pathogenic bacteria, posing significant public health risks when consumed raw or inadequately washed. This study aimed to isolate and evaluate the antimicrobial resistance profiles of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* in popular leafy vegetables from open markets in Abakaliki, Nigeria. Fifteen vegetable samples, including *Ugu*, Green, Curry, Scent, and Bitter leaf, were analyzed using standard microbiological techniques for bacterial isolation and enumeration of colonies. Antibiotic resistance was assessed via the Kirby-Bauer disc-diffusion method. Cultural, morphological, and biochemical tests confirmed the identities of the isolates. Results indicated significant colonies enumeration, with average counts exceeding 1.3×10^1 CFU/ml for *Staphylococcus aureus* and 3.6×10^1 CFU/ml for *Escherichia coli*. Results revealed high contamination levels, with 60% of samples positive for *E. coli* and 86.7% for *S. aureus*, including 60% co-contamination with both pathogens. *E. coli* exhibited 100% susceptibility to Gentamicin, with high resistance to Tetracycline (66.7%) and Cotrimoxazole (55.5%). *S. aureus* showed 92.3% susceptibility to Gentamycin, Chloramphenicol, and Ciprofloxacin but significant resistance to Erythromycin (61.5%), Ampicillin, and Cloxacillin (53.9%). Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI) values indicated moderate to high resistance among isolates. These findings underscore the urgent need for improved hygiene practices in vegetable handling and stricter regulations to mitigate antibiotic resistance and foodborne disease risks in Abakaliki.

Keywords: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, antibiotic resistance, leafy vegetables

INTRODUCTION

Leafy vegetables are an essential component of a healthy diet, providing vital nutrients such as vitamins, minerals, and phytonutrients that support metabolic functions (WHO, 2020; Udu-Ibiam *et al.*, 2022). Despite their nutritional benefits, fresh vegetables can serve as vectors for pathogenic microorganisms, particularly when consumed raw or inadequately washed (Biswas *et al.*, 2020). In many regions, including Nigeria, leafy vegetables are often sold untreated and exposed to unsanitary conditions during production, transportation, and vending, increasing the risk of microbial contamination (Losio *et al.*, 2015). Among the pathogens of concern, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* are particularly significant due to their association with foodborne illnesses and increasing antibiotic resistance (Joseph *et al.*, 2023; Orji *et al.*, 2024; Orji *et al.*, 2025). Vegetables typically have 10^4 to 10^7 or 10^3 to 10^5 microorganisms/cm³ or microorganisms/g. Several of the most common bacteria kinds include *Corynebacterium*, lactic acid bacteria, *Proteus*, *Micrococcus*, *Enterococcus* and *Pseudomonas* (Sharma *et al.*, 2023).

E. coli, a common indicator of faecal contamination, is linked to diarrheal diseases, while *S. aureus* a ubiquitous skin and nasal microbiota can produce heat-stable enterotoxins that cause food poisoning (Kothe *et al.*, 2023; Peter *et al.*, 2024). Contamination of vegetables can occur through multiple routes, including contaminated irrigation water, unhygienic handling, and exposure to soil or animal waste (Bishop and Okwori, 2017). Furthermore, the misuse of antibiotics in both clinical and agricultural settings has exacerbated the emergence of multidrug-resistant strains, limiting treatment options for infections (Nomeh *et al.*, 2023).

In Abakaliki, Nigeria, where open markets are a primary source of fresh produce, there is limited data on the microbial quality of leafy vegetables and the antibiotic resistance profiles of associated pathogens. Previous studies in other regions have documented high levels of contamination and antimicrobial resistance in fresh produce, highlighting the need for localized assessments (Obeng *et al.*, 2018; Yafetto *et al.*, 2019; Udu-Ibiam *et al.*, 2022). This study therefore aims to: (a) isolate and quantify *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in commonly consumed leafy vegetables (e. g., *Ugu*, green, scent, bitter leaves and curry) from Abakaliki Markets; and (b) evaluate their antibiotic resistance patterns to assess resistance trends and provide evidence-based recommendations to improve food safety and public health practices. By addressing these objectives, this study contributes to the growing body of research on foodborne pathogens and antimicrobial resistance in Nigeria, while informing policy and consumer awareness initiatives to mitigate health risks associated with contaminated vegetables.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study location and description

The study was conducted in Abakaliki, situated at Latitude 6° 19' 60.00" N and Longitude 8° 05' 60.00" E. According to the United Nations (2024), the current metropolitan population of Abakaliki in 2024 is estimated at 693,000 (Nwojiji *et al.*, 2025a). The residents primarily engage in farming and petty trading as key economic activities. Market Selection and Characteristics: Samples for this study were collected from two prominent markets in Abakaliki: the Kpiri-Kpiri Market and the International Market. Both markets are located in densely populated areas. The International Market, in particular, is a larger, ultramodern central marketplace that serves not only Abakaliki but also surrounding suburbs and much of Ebonyi State.

Collection of Sample

Fifteen fresh leafy vegetable samples, comprising five different types *Ugu* (pumpkin), scent leaf, green vegetable (African spinach), bitter leaf, and curry leaf were collected in duplicates from various vendors at the International Market in Abakaliki. Each sample was placed in a sterile polythene bag (manufactured by Aqua Rapha Investment Nigeria Limited, Enugu, Nigeria) and immediately transferred in cooled containers to the laboratory. The samples were then transported to the Department of Microbiology for further analysis. All analyses were conducted within 1–2 hours of collection to ensure sample integrity.

Processing of Vegetable Samples

Stock solutions were prepared from vegetable samples following the methodology described by Yafetto *et al.* (2019). Briefly, 10 g of *Ugu* leaves were weighed, washed with sterile distilled water, and transferred into a 250 mL conical flask. Subsequently, 90 mL of sterile 0.85% normal saline (diluent) was added. The mixture was gently agitated for 5 minutes to dislodge surface-adhered microorganisms. The resulting suspension was decanted and used as the stock solution for serial dilution. Serial dilutions were prepared by aseptically transferring 1 mL of the stock solution into a test tube containing 9 mL of sterile distilled water (10^{-1} dilution). Using a sterile micropipette, this process was repeated sequentially to obtain dilutions of 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-5} (Joseph *et al.*, 2023). The same procedure was replicated for the remaining four vegetable types to ensure consistency in sample preparation for microbiological analysis.

Inoculation and Isolation of Bacteria from Leafy Vegetables

Serially diluted sample of dilution factor 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} was used for bacterial isolation. Aliquot (0.5 ml) from each 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} dilution were pipetted onto two separate sterile Petri dish before 20ml of sterile Mannitol salt agar (Thermo Scientific™, U. S.A) and Eosin methylene blue Agar (EMB) (Thermo Scientific™, U. S.A) was added onto the plates and mixed well. After which it was incubated at 37°C for 24 hr. After overnight incubation colonies were counted and reported as according to Joseph *et al.* (2023). These colonies with golden-yellow and greenish metallic sheen on Mannitol salt agar (Thermo Scientific™, U. S.A) and Eosin methylene blue Agar (EMB) (Thermo Scientific™, U. S.A) respectively were sub-cultured through successive streaking and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to obtain pure cultures. The isolates were further characterized using standard microbiological techniques, including Gram staining, motility testing, methyl red test, Voges-Proskauer test, citrate utilization, oxidase test, indole test, triple sugar iron (TSI) test, methyl red test, and carbohydrate fermentation tests (lactose, sucrose, mannitol, glucose) (Iroha *et al.*, 2019; Nwojiji *et al.*, 2025a; Nwojiji *et al.*, 2025b). For definitive identification, the isolates were analyzed using the VITEK 2 automated system (bioMérieux, France) in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions (Nwojiji *et al.*, 2025b). This comprehensive approach ensured accurate identification of the bacterial species.

Antimicrobial Resistance Testing of Bacteria from Leafy Vegetables

Antibiotic susceptibility of the isolates was determined using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion Method (CLSI, 2022; Nwojiji *et al.*, 2025b). Bacteria inoculum equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standard of the isolate was streaked on entire Mueller-Hinton agar (Thermo Scientific™, U. S.A) plate, the following conventional antibiotics; Cotrimoxazole (25 µg), Erythromycin (15 µg), Ampicillin (30 µg), Tetracycline (30 µg), Streptomycin (25 µg), Ciprofloxacin (5 µg), Ofloxacin (5 µg), Piperacillin (30 µg), ceftriaxone (30 µg), Roxithromycin (15 µg), Levofloxacin (5 µg), Cloxacillin 30 µg), Chloramphenicol (5 µg), Gentamicin (15 µg) were impregnated aseptically on

the plate. After overnight incubation at 37°C, zone of inhibition was measured and interpreted as Resistant (R) and Susceptible (S) to each of the tested antibiotic (CLSI, 2022; Nwojji *et al.*, 2025b).

Determination of Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index

The multiple antibiotic resistant indexes (MARI) for each isolates were equally derived using the mathematical expression of Edemekong *et al.* (2022) and John-Onwe *et al.* (2023), which is given as:

$$\text{MAR index} = a/b$$

Where **a**- represent the number of antibiotics to which the isolates was resistant

b- The total number of antibiotics against which an individual isolate was tested

RESULTS

Mean Bacterial Counts of Leafy Vegetables Obtained From International Market, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

The bacterial contamination levels of *Staphylococcus* spp. and *E. coli* in various leafy vegetables from the International Market are summarized in Table 1. Spinach samples from Lot 1 exhibited the highest microbial loads, with mean *Staphylococcus* spp. and coliform counts of 4.4×10^4 CFU/g and 8.3×10^2 CFU/g, respectively. Across all samples, *Staphylococcus aureus* counts ranged from 1.3×10^1 CFU/g to 4.4×10^4 CFU/g, while coliform counts varied between 1.5×10^1 CFU/g and 8.3×10^2 CFU/g. These findings indicate significant variation in bacterial contamination levels among the sampled vegetables, with spinach demonstrating the highest degree of contamination.

Cultural, Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics of Bacteria Isolated From Different Spoiled Vegetables

The isolated bacteria were identified through comprehensive analysis of their cultural, morphological, and biochemical characteristics, as detailed in Table 2. From the initial screening on Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) and Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) media, 60 presumptive Staphylococcal and coliform isolates were randomly selected for species-level identification. Subsequent characterization revealed that among these isolates: 13 were confirmed as *Staphylococcus aureus* and 9 were identified as *Escherichia coli*

Occurrences of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* based on type of Vegetables from different Location

The occurrence of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* across different vegetable types and sampling locations is presented in Tables 3 and 4. Among the 15 samples representing five leafy vegetable varieties: *E. coli* was detected in 9 samples (60.0% prevalence). *S. aureus* showed higher contamination, appearing in 13 samples (80.0% prevalence). Co-contamination with both pathogens occurred in 9 samples. *Ugu* (pumpkin leaves) and scent leaf exhibited the highest contamination levels. Green vegetables from three locations showed significant pathogen presence. While samples from Abakaliki International Market recorded the highest *Staphylococcus* counts (Table 1), this did not consistently correlate with prevalence patterns across all sites (Table 2).

Antibiotics Resistance profile of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates From Leafy Vegetable Sold Within International Market, Abakaliki

The antibiotic resistance patterns of the bacterial isolates are presented in Table 5. Among nine *E. coli* isolates tested against a panel of 12 antibiotics, the following susceptibility profile was observed: Most effective antibiotics Gentamicin demonstrated 100% efficacy against all isolates. High susceptibility was observed for: Chloramphenicol (10 µg): 88.9% (8/9 isolates); Ciprofloxacin 88.9% (8/9 isolates), Levofloxacin (10 µg): 77.8% (7/9 isolates). Moderately effective antibiotics (66.7% susceptibility): Ceftriaxone, Roxithromycin and Ampicillin. The highest resistance patterns was against Tetracycline: 66.7% resistance (6/9 isolates) and Cotrimoxazole 55.6% resistance (5/9 isolates). Analysis of 13 *S. aureus* isolates against 12 antibiotics revealed: highest susceptibility to Gentamicin at 92.3% (12/13 isolates). Moderate susceptibility to Chloramphenicol: 84.6% (11/13) and Ciprofloxacin 76.9% (10/13). A significant resistance to Erythromycin accounted: 61.5% (8/13) and Ampicillin and Cloxacillin 53.9% (7/13 each).

Antibiotics Resistant Pattern, Multiple Antibiotic resistant Index (MARI) of *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Vegetables Sold within International Market, Abakaliki

The Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI) analysis demonstrated: resistance spectrum with CL1-E showed highest resistance (MARI 0.6; resistant to 6/12 antibiotics) and SL1-E exhibited minimal resistance (MARI 0.1; resistant to 1/12 antibiotics) as shown in Table 6. The distribution profile revealed that **40% of isolates showed moderate resistance (MARI 0.3–0.5) while 20% displayed high resistance (MARI ≥0.5)**

Clinical Implications: The observed resistance patterns, particularly: the 50% resistance rate in CL1-E and elevated MARI values (>0.2) in 60% of isolates. Suggest significant antibiotic exposure in these environments, potentially compromising treatment efficacy for foodborne infections.

Antibiotics Resistant Pattern and Multiple Antibiotic resistant Index (MARI) of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates from Vegetable Sold within International Market, Abakaliki.

Table 7 presents the comprehensive antibiotic resistance patterns of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates against a panel of 12 antibiotics. The analysis reveals distinct resistance profiles among the isolates, as characterized by their Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI) values ranging from 0 to 0.5.

Highly Resistant Isolates (MARI 0.5): BL1-S, BL3-S, SL1-S, and SL3-S demonstrated resistance to 6-7 antibiotics. These isolates represent significant multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains

Moderately Resistant Isolates (MARI 0.2): UG3-S and SL2-S showed limited resistance patterns. This suggests origin from environments with minimal antibiotic exposure

Fully Susceptible Isolate: CL2-S exhibited complete susceptibility (MARI 0) to all tested antibiotics

Discussion

While vegetable consumption offers numerous health benefits, it is not without risks if proper hygienic practices are not followed during handling and consumption. The primary threat posed by vegetables is the potential for infections and food poisoning. Many consumers fail to adequately wash or process vegetables after purchase, increasing their risk of exposure to pathogens (Baishakhi *et al.*, 2020).

Bacterial Contamination in Fresh Vegetables

This study highlights that fresh vegetables can harbour pathogenic bacteria, acting as potential vectors for disease transmission. All tested samples were contaminated with *Staphylococcal* and coliform strains. The highest microbial counts were observed in green vegetables (*A. spinach*) from Lot 1, with mean *Staphylococcus* and coliform counts of 4.4×10^4 CFU/g and 8.3×10^2 CFU/g, respectively. The *Staphylococcus* counts ranged from 1.3×10^1 to 4.4×10^4 CFU/g, while coliform counts varied between 1.5×10^1 (lowest) and 8.3×10^2 (highest). These elevated levels indicate unhygienic conditions in open markets.

Among the pathogens examined, *Staphylococcus aureus* contamination was more prevalent than *Escherichia coli*. Although *S. aureus* is part of the normal skin and nail microbiota, it can cause various infections. Human contact facilitates its transfer to vegetables, making it a significant foodborne pathogen. *S. aureus* has been implicated in outbreaks worldwide (Seo *et al.*, 2010; Hong *et al.*, 2015; Al-Kharousi *et al.*, 2016; Kothe *et al.*, 2021). For instance, it was detected in 25% of ready-to-eat foods in China (Wang *et al.*, 2014) and linked to over 20% of fruit and vegetable outbreaks in Brazil (Elias *et al.*, 2008).

S. aureus produces heat-resistant enterotoxins that damage host cell membranes, leading to foodborne illnesses. A population of 5 log CFU/g is sufficient to produce harmful toxin levels (Lindqvist *et al.*, 2002), a threshold easily reached through improper handling and storage. Contamination often occurs when buyers excessively handle vegetables during selection, transferring bacteria from their hands to the produce.

Risks of Enteropathogenic E. coli infections

This study also associates vegetable consumption with increased risks of enteropathogenic *E. coli* infections. Previous research by Heaton and Jones (2008) confirmed the presence of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in ready-to-eat salads, aligning with findings by Bishop and Okwori (2017), who identified bacterial contamination in carrots. Potential contamination sources include soil, feces, irrigation water, dust, insects, manure, animal waste, and human handling.

Of the 15 leafy vegetable samples analyzed, 60% were contaminated with *E. coli*, while 80% harbored *S. aureus*. Nine samples showed co-contamination by both pathogens. The highest contamination levels were found in *Ugu* and Scent leaf, followed by green vegetables across three locations. Despite higher microbial counts in samples from Abakaliki International Market, pathogen prevalence varied by site. The significant bacterial presence underscores a public health concern, necessitating immediate intervention to prevent foodborne outbreaks. Similar findings have been reported by other researchers (Sahilah *et al.*, 2010; Tunung *et al.*, 2011).

Antibiotic Resistance Patterns

E. coli isolates displayed highest susceptibility to Gentamicin (10 µg) recording 100% effectiveness. Moderate susceptibility was observed against Chloramphenicol (10 µg) and Ciprofloxacin (10 µg) 88.9%. Over 60% susceptibility were seen as follows: Levofloxacin (77.7%), Ceftriaxone (66.7%), Roxithromycin (66.7%), and Ampicillin (66.7%). While the highest resistance was seen against Tetracycline (30 µg) –66.7%, and Cotrimoxazole (30 µg) 55.5%.

S. aureus isolates showed highest susceptibility to Gentamicin (10 µg) 92.3%, Moderate susceptibility to Chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin (10 µg) and demonstrated highest resistance to Erythromycin (61.5%), followed by Ampicillin (53.9%) and Cloxacillin (53.9%).

The high resistance to erythromycin and ampicillin likely stems from their widespread use in infection prevention and first-line treatments (Nwode *et al.*, 2024). In contrast, low resistance to gentamicin may be due to its controlled parenteral administration. Overuse of low-toxicity antibiotics (e.g., tetracycline, sulfonamides, β-lactams) has contributed to rising resistance (Titilawo, 2015). These findings contrast with Oyediji *et al.* (2011), who reported no ciprofloxacin resistance in enteric bacteria but noted high ampicillin resistance consistent with other studies (Tula and Osaretin, 2014; Nwode *et al.*, 2024).

Multidrug Resistance and Public Health Implications

E. coli Resistance Profiles (Table 9) with **MARI values:** Ranged from **0.1 to 0.6**, indicating moderate to high resistance. **CL1-E** was the most resistant isolate (MARI 0.6), resistant to **50% of tested antibiotics**. **SL1-E** demonstrated the least resistant (MARI 0.1).

S. aureus Resistance Profiles (Table 8) with **MARI values:** Ranged from **0 to 0.5**. **High-resistance isolates (BL1-S, BL3-S, SL1-S, SL3-S):** Resistant to **6–7 antibiotics** (MARI 0.5). **Low-resistance isolates (UG3-S, SL2-S):** MARI 0.2. **CL2-S:** Fully susceptible (MARI 0). The presence of multidrug-resistant strains suggests exposure to antibiotic-heavy environments, complicating treatment options. Many isolates likely acquired resistance genes from other organisms, including extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) producers.

Drivers of Antibiotic Resistance

The observed resistance patterns reflect widespread antibiotic misuse in clinical and environmental settings (Olukosi *et al.*, 2016). Contributing factors include: Over-the-counter antibiotic sales, inappropriate prescribing practices, poor regulatory oversight and substandard drugs exerting sub-inhibitory selective pressure. Antibiotic-resistant bacteria in vegetables pose a serious public health risk, as they can transfer resistance genes to human gut flora, exacerbating resistance challenges. These bacteria also serve as reservoirs for persistent resistance genes (Olukosi *et al.*, 2016).

CONCLUSION

The study highlights significant bacteria contamination of leafy vegetables sold in Abakaliki Markets, with *Staphylococcus aureus* (86.7%) more prevalent than *Escherichia coli* (60%). Co-contamination was observed in 60% of samples, emphasizing the dual risk posed by these pathogens. Antibiotic resistance profiling revealed concerning patterns: *E. coli* isolates were highly resistant to Tetracycline and Cotrimoxazole, while *S. aureus* exhibited notable resistance to Erythromycin, Ampicillin, and Cloxacillin. Gentamycin remained effective against both pathogens, suggesting its potential as a treatment option. The high MARI values among isolates indicate exposure to antibiotic-heavy environments, likely due to misuse in clinical and agricultural settings. These findings underscore the public health risks associated with consuming

contaminated vegetables and call for immediate interventions, including vendor education on hygiene, improved market sanitation, and regulatory measures to curb antibiotic misuse. Addressing these issues is critical to safeguarding food safety and reducing the burden of antibiotic-resistant infections in the region.

APPENDIX

Table 1: Mean Microbial Counts of Leafy Vegetables Obtained from International Market, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

Mean MSA strains and EMS strains Bacterial Counts (Cfu/g)				
S/N	Vegetable samples	Sample Code	Yellow Colonies on MSA	Deep pink Colonies on E.M.B
1.	<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin) from (Lot1)	UG1	6.9×10^3	4.8×10^2
2.	<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin) from (Lot 2)	UG2	2.4×10^2	1.5×10^1
3.	<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin) from (Lot 3)	UG1	7.6×10^2	6.4×10^1
4.	Bitter leaf (Lot 1)	BL1	2.3×10^2	1.6×10^2
5.	Bitter leaf (Lot 2)	BL2	3.2×10^2	4.3×10^2
6.	Bitter leaf (Lot 3)	BL3	2.4×10^2	2.9×10^2
7.	Scent leaf, (Lot 1)	SL1	8.7×10^2	5.4×10^2
8.	Scent leaf, (Lot 2)	SL2	4.2×10^2	6.3×10^1
9.	Scent leaf, (Lot 3)	SL3	2.8×10^2	1.8×10^1
10.	Green vegetable (A. spinach) (Lot 1)	GR1	4.4×10^4	8.3×10^2
11.	Green vegetable (A. spinach) (Lot 2)	GR2	2.8×10^2	3.1×10^2
12.	Green vegetable (A. spinach) (Lot 3)	GR3	1.30×10^2	1.8×10^2
13.	Curry leaf (Lot 1)	CL1	1.3×10^1	1.9×10^1
14./	Curry leaf (Lot 2)	CL2	4.2×10^2	3.6×10^1
15.	Curry leaf (Lot 3)	CL3	6.7×10^2	4.2×10^1

KEY: E.M.B- Eosine methylene Blue Agar, **MSA-** Mannitol Salt Agar

Table 2: Cultural, Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from Vegetables sold in International Market, Abakaliki, Nigeria

TOTAL NUMBER OF CONFIRMED ISOLATES (N = 22)	
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

Cultural Characteristics	Greenish Metallic Sheen On Emb.	Creamy Yellow Colonies On Mannitol Salt Agar.
Gram Reaction	-VE	+VE
Morphology	Short rod	Cluster cocci
Catalase Test	+VE	+VE
Oxidase Test	-VE	+VE
Citrate Test	-VE	+VE
Coagulase Test	-VE	+VE
Indole Test	+VE	+VE
Voges-Proskauer Test	-VE	+VE
Methyl Red Test	-VE	+VE
Carbohydrate Fermentation		
Glucose	AG	A
Sucrose	A	A
Lactose	AG	A
Mannitol	-VE	+VE

KEY: AG-acid & gas, A-acid, +VE-present and -VE- absent

Table 3: Prevalence of *E.coli* and *S. aureus* and their co-contaminations on leafy Vegetable sold in International Market, Abakaliki, Nigeria

Vegetable samples	Sample Code	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Co-contaminations
<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin) from (Lot 1)	UG1	+	+	+
<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin) from (Lot 2)	UG2	-	+	+
<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin) from (Lot 3)	UG3	+	+	+
Bitter leaf (Lot 1)	BL1	-	+	-
Bitter leaf (Lot 2)	BL2	+	-	-
Bitter leaf (Lot 3)	BL3	-	+	-
Scent leaf, (Lot 1)	SL1	+	+	+
Scent leaf, (Lot 2)	SL2	-	+	-
Scent leaf, (Lot 3)	SL3	+	+	+
Green vegetable (Africa spinach) (Lot 1)	GR1	+	+	+
Green vegetable (Africa spinach) (Lot 2)	GR2	+	+	+

Green vegetable (Africa spinach) (Lot 3)	GR3	+	+	+
Curry leaf (Lot 1)	CL1	+	-	-
Curry leaf (Lot 2)	CL2	-	+	-
Curry leaf (Lot 3)	CL3	-	+	+
Number (%) Positive Sample		9 (60.0)	13 (86.7)	8 (60)

Table 4: Occurrences of *E.coli* and *S. aureus* based on type of Vegetables from different Location

Vegetable samples	Number of Samples Examined	Number (%) Containing <i>E.coli</i>	Number (%) containing <i>S. aureus</i>
<i>Ugu</i> (pumpkin)	3	2 (66.7)	3 (100)
Bitter leaf	3	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)
Scent leaf	3	2 (66.7)	3 (33.3)
Green vegetable	3	2 (66.7)	2 (66.7)
Curry leaf	3	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)
Total sample Positive Sample (%)	15	9 (60.0)	13 (86.7)

Table 5: Antibiotics Resistance profile of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates From Leafy Vegetable Sold Within International Market, Abakaliki

Antibiotics Disc (μg)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n =9)			<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (n =13)		
	S (%)	I (%)	R (%)	S (%)	I (%)	R (%)
Cotrimoxazole (25)	2 (22.2)	2 (22.2)	5 (55.51)	8(61.5)	1 (7.7)	4(30.8)
Erythromycin (15)	NA	NA	NA	4(30.8)	1 (7.7)	8(61.5)
Ampicillin (10)	6 (66.7)	2 (22.2)	1 (11.1)	3 (23.1)	3 (23.1)	7(53.9)
Tetracycline (30)	1 (11.1)	2 (22.2)	6 (66.7)	5 (38.5)	3 (23.1)	5 (38.5)
Streptomycin (30)	NA	NA	NA	7(53.9)	2(15.4)	4(30.8)
Cefotaxime (10)	5 (55.51)	1 (11.1)	3 (33.3)	NA	NA	NA
Ciprofloxacin (10)	8 (88.9)	1 (11.1)	0(0.0)	11(84.6)	1 (7.7)	1 (7.7)
Ofloxacin (10)	3 (33.3)	3 (33.3)	3 (33.3)	10(76.9)	2(15.4)	1 (7.7)
Roxithromycin (15)	6 (66.7)	0(0.0)	3 (33.3)	6(46.15)	4(30.8)	3 (23.1)
Levofloxacin (10)	7 (77.7)	0(0.0)	2 (22.2)	10(76.9)	0(0.0)	3 (23.1)
Ceftriaxone (10)	6 (66.7)	1 (18.75)	2 (22.2)	NA	NA	NA
Cloxacillin (5)	NA	NA	NA	5 (38.5)	1 (7.7)	7(53.9)

Piperacillin (10)	4 (44.4)	3 (33.3)	2 (22.2)	NA	NA	NA
Chloramphenicol (30)	8 (88.9)	1 (6.25)	0 (5.0)	11(84.6)	2(15.4)	0(0.0)
Gentamicin (10)	9 (100.0)	0 (12.5)	0(6.25)	12(92.3)	1 (7.7)	0(0.0)

Key: **S-** Susceptible, **I-** Intermediate, **R-**Resistance, **NA-**Not Applicable, **%-** Percentage, **µg-** microgram, **n-**number of isolate.

Table 6: Antibiotics Resistant Pattern, Multiple Antibiotic resistant Index (MARI) of *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Vegetables Sold within International Market, Abakaliki

<i>Escherichia coli</i> (N =9)				
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	No. of Antibiotics	Resistant Pattern	MARI	(%) Resistant to 12 Antibiotic
UG1-E	9	BA-TE	0.2	16.7
UG1-E	9	BA- AS- TE-CF	0.3	33.3
BL2-E	9	TE- OF-LE- PT	0.3	33.3
SL1-E	9	LE	0.1	8.3
SL3-E	9	BA-AS- OF- RO- CR	0.4	41.7
GR1-E	9	AS-TE-RO- PT	0.3	33.3
GR2-E	9	BA- CF	0.2	16.7
GR3-E	9	AS- TE	0.2	16.7
CL1-E	9	BA-AS- CF- OF- RO-LE	0.6	50.0

Key: MARI- Multiple Antibiotic resistant Index, **Antibiotics Used** Cotrimoxazole (BA) 25 µg, Erythromycin (E) 15 µg, Ampicillin (AS) 10 µg, Tetracycline (TE) 30 µg, Streptomycin (S) 10 µg, Ciprofloxacin (CP) 5 µg, Ofloxacin (OF) 5 µg, Roxithromycin (RO) 15 µg, Levofloxacin (LE) 5 µg, Cloxacillin (CX) 1 µg, Chloramphenicol (C) 30 µg, Gentamicin (GN) 10 µg.

Table 7: Antibiotics Resistant Pattern and Multiple Antibiotic resistant Index (MARI) of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates from Vegetable Sold Within International Market, Abakaliki

<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> isolates Code	Antibiotics Tested	Resistant Pattern	MARI	(%) Resistant to 12 Antibiotic
UG1-S	12	BA- E- TE-CF	0.3	30.8
UG2-S	12	TE- OF-LE- RO -PT- S- CX	0.3	53.8
UG3-S	12	E-CX	0.2	15.4
BL1-S	12	BA-E-AS-OF-CR-S-CP	0.5	53.8
BL3-S	12	AS-E-TE-RO- PT- CX	0.5	50
SL1-S	12	BA-E-S-RO-CF-CX	0.5	50
SL2-S	12	AS- TE	0.2	15.4
SL3-S	12	BA-E-AS-CF-OF-LE	0.5	50.0
GR1-S	12	TE- S- RO -CX	0.3	30.8
GR2-S	12	E- AS- TE- S	0.3	30.8
GR3-S	12	E- AS-LE- CX	0.3	30.8
CL2-S	12	0	0	0
CL3-S	12	E- AS- CX	0.2	23.1

Key: MARI- Multiple Antibiotic resistant Index, **Antibiotics Used** Cotrimoxazole (BA) 25 µg, Erythromycin (E) 15 µg, Ampicillin (AS) 10 µg, Tetracycline (TE) 30 µg, Streptomycin (S) 10 µg, Ciprofloxacin (CP) 5 µg, Ofloxacin (OF) 5 µg, Roxithromycin (RO) 15 µg, Levofloxacin (LE) 10 µg, Cloxacillin (CX) 5 µg, Chloramphenicol (C) 30 µg, Gentamicin (GN) 10 µg.

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